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The Effect of Work Motivation and Compensation on the Non-State Employees' Work Performance with Work Satisfaction as Intervening Variables at the National Land Agency, the Regency of Bekasi

Sri Marti Pramudena¹, Ahmad Badawi Saluy², Abdul Muhith³

¹ Magister Management, Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: dena_pramu@mercubuana.ac.id

² Magister Management, Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: ahmad.badawi@mercubuana.ac.id

³ Magister Management, Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: abdulmuhith1996@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aimed to examine and analyze the effect of work motivation and compensation on the employees' work performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable conducted at the National Land Agency, the Regency of Bekasi. The research used a quantitative descriptive method with a sample of 103 respondents out of a population consisting of 140 employees. Meanwhile, the data analysis was conducted using the coefficient of determination and simultaneous coefficient. Based on the study results, it reveals that (i) job motivation partially has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, (ii) compensation partially has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, (iii) job motivation partially has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, performance, (iv) compensation partially have a positive and significant effect on work performance, (v) job satisfaction partially has a positive and significant effect on work performance, (vi) work motivation and compensation simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, (vii) work motivation and compensation simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on work performance. The two independent variables, i.e., work motivation and compensation, have a partial effect and can also work together (simultaneously) and have a positive and significant effect which can be proven by all the results of the proven hypotheses.

Keywords: Work Motivation, Compensation, Job Satisfaction, Work Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

In search of capacity enhancement, an organization takes several actions, such as learning, upgrading or training, providing appropriate rewards, and sharing motivation. In this way, it is expected that employees will further optimize their responsibility for their profession because they have been provided with learning and training relevant to their profession. On the other hand, provisioning rewards and motivational activities are basically the

employees' rights. It is the institutional responsibility to support the participation of its employees in achieving goals formalized by the institution.

In Indonesian people's perspective, land is a vital in the nation and state's life. The bond between the people and the land office has long existed in a close relationship. All areas of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI) are the homeland of the totality of the Indonesian Nation. Homeland is therefore ties of the Republic of Indonesia. Thus, in this national context, it is necessary for land regulation to protect the sustainability of the life system of the nation and state.

Fundamental values in the land aspect are also enacted in TAP MPR Number IX or 2001 regarding Agrarian Reform and Management of Natural Energy Resource and Law Number 5 year 1960 concerning Fundamental Agrarian Regulations, Presidential Decree No. 10 year 2006 regarding the Land Affairs Agency of the Republic of Indonesia is a form of strengthening the national land institution to establish a constitutional mandate in the land affairs.

Currently, the National Land Agency is demanded to have competent employees for institutional development. The organization must be able to create and improve their capabilities in their environment. Several aspects influence its success; one of the most determining factors is its human resources since the resource performs the totality from the level of programming to the assessment. Human resources can utilize other sources within an organization or institution. In an organization, the human resource plays a very significant role that can carry out organizational activities.

Poor performance of human resources results from a lack of employees' motivation at the National Land Agency, such as at the workplace. For instance, there are some employees who leave their work during working hours, causing unresolved works. Thus, there is an urgent need to elevate their work motivation to do their task appropriately.

To examine more deeply about motivation in the office, the authors conducted a pre-survey at the office location. It was found that work motivation was the selected factor chosen by the respondents as the most influential factor in their performance. During the presurvey activity, the total sample accounted for 103 respondents from a total population of 140 employees. The results of following pre-survey are presented in the following table.

Table 1: Pre-survey results on employees' work motivation

No.	Questions	Yes		No	
		(%)	Amount	(%)	Amount
1	Weekly allowance is sufficient for transportation cost to office.	37.86%	39	62.14%	64
2	Office provides enough facilities.	73.79%	76	26.21%	27
3	My superior always gives instruction during work	45.63%	47	54.37%	56
4	I feel comfortable a workplace environment	80.58%	83	19.42%	20
Average		59.47%	61	40.53%	42

Source: processed presurvey results, 2020

Motivation plays a meaningful matter for employees since motivated employees desire to feel happier, fresher and are willing to arrive at office for work. The lack of motivation may lead to severe consequences on the level of employees' attendance and participation. Therefore, an organization is required to pay close attention to the employees' motivation so that they do not carry out their duties at will while there is no professional debt.

Meanwhile, rewards are a method an organization can provide as a form of reply to its employees. Since rewards can increase or decrease employee's competence, providing rewards to employees needs more attention from an institution. Rewards must be on a solid, correct, and balanced basis. When the rewards are experienced unbalanced, they will experience feelings of disappointment. As a result, good employees want to leave the organization.

For instance, there is an employee who has worked for more than 10 years with a new employee. Their salary is comparable for both old employees and the new ones since the new employee is assigned with heavier tasks than the old ones. Therefore, these employees are not satisfied with their work and their performance is not in line with the organization's expectations. Thus, in this aspect, the agency must take a reward for these employees taken into consideration. To delve more deeply into compensation in the office, the authors conducted a pre-survey on compensation. Based on the results, the 103 respondents out of the total population of 140 employees regarded the compensation as the most influential factor in their performance. The pre-survey results are presented in the following table.

Table 2: Presurvey results on the role of compensation

No.	Questions	Yes		No	
		(%)	Amount	(%)	Amount
1	My income can fulfill my needs.	42.72%	44	57.28%	59
2	I am glad to have extra income from my employer due to my good work performance	63.11%	65	36.89%	38
3	I am satisfied with compensation the office provides	38.83%	40	61.17%	63
4	I feel secured since I get health insurance during my work period	88.35%	91	11.65%	12
Average		58.25%	60	41.75%	43

Source: presurvey results, 2020

By this procedure, individual actions and behavior with feelings of pleasure and enjoyment can be revealed. Generally, the method can make them carry out good deeds by repeatedly intending to make a person continue to be active in an effort to justify or improve the results he has achieved. A research conducted by Purnami (2014) reported that rewards could positively affect an employee to increase his ability. It means that the rewards will continue to increase the employees' motivation in achieving great competence as well. Likewise, another research also reported that there were consequences of rewards for employee abilities.

A research conducted by Dhermawan (2012) reported that rewards are proven to result in positive and important consequences for employees to improve their abilities. It means that the rewards improvement an organization is going to provide will result in an enhanced ability of its employees. On the contrary, if there is a lack of rewards an institution provides to employees, the employees' ability tends to reduce. There is a distinct lack of employee's ability at the Office since many employees postpone their tasks or do their duty at will. If the Office aspires to achieve good employees' performance, there is a need to conduct an assessment and gather information regarding the situation to estimate in policies and decisions making. To examine more deeply about the employees' performance, a pre-survey was conducted with 103 respondents on which factors most influenced the work performance at the BPN office in the Regency of Bekasi. The results are presented in the following table.

Table 3: The most influential factors to work performance

No	Factor	%	No. respondents
1	Compensation	26,21%	27
2	Job satisfaction	23,31%	24
3	Motivation	21,36%	22
4	Work discipline	14,56%	15
5	Workload	9,71%	10
6	Workplace environment	4,85%	5
Total		100%	103

Source: presurvey results processed, 2020

Based on the presurvey results on the aspects affecting work performance in Table 1.3, it can be observed that motivation (21.36%), compensation (26.21%), and job satisfaction (23.31%) are among the most influential for the National Land Agency office, the Regency of Bekasi.

The employees' competence is required to improve productivity and protect the organizational development. Without compensation, each institution does not intend to provide its employees. It is one of the significant problems in delivering motivation for the employees because to improve their capabilities; proper compensation is required to support them. When there is a decrease in employees' competence, it will have negative consequences for the organization.

Job satisfaction greatly requires an employer to motivate through a need, which is one meaningful aspect for motivating employees. It is because as people, the employees have various basic necessities and needs. They will be motivated when their needs are fulfilled. Thus, by fulfilling their desires, their satisfaction is eventually increased during their activities. This situation will have a positive impact on the employees' competence.

Employees who work exceeding their working hours or also known as overtime lack attention from an agency. Therefore, they are not satisfied at work. In fact, the agency should pay attention to the employees' work performance to complete their overtime job by providing appropriate compensation. Thus, they will feel satisfied and have enthusiasm at work.

To examine more deeply about what aspects determining their job satisfaction in the office, we conducted a pre-survey at the office. There were total 103 samples selected as the respondents out of 140 total population. The results are presented in the following table.

By providing adequate compensation to employees that their needs will be fulfilled, it is expected they are satisfied at work. Dissatisfaction caused by their unfulfilled needs at work will decrease their job satisfaction, resulting in employees' poor work performance. Job satisfaction refers to contentedness to income, promotion, leadership abilities, areas of activity and supervision with employees having a great influence in improving their performance. Job satisfaction leads the employees to be more enthusiastic at workplace so that they are more active in achieving targets (Pramudena, 2019). In addition, job satisfaction can also instill a strong commitment to the employees.

Table 4: Pre-survey results on job satisfaction

No	Statement	Yes		No	
		(%)	Amount	(%)	Amount
1	There is gradual socialization on work policies at workplace	54.37%	56	45.63%	47
2	Honor earned equivalent with tasks when done overtime.	40.78%	42	59.22%	61
3	Work comfortably with co-workers	64.08%	66	35.92%	37

4	Holiday allowance is given based on employees' period of employment	44.66%	46	55.34%	57
Average		50.97%	53	49.03%	50

Source: presurvey result processed, 2020

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Work motivation

According to Hasibuan (2012), work motivation is the provision of driving energy that results in the excitement to an individual in performing activities so that he is willing to work passionately, efficiently, and put all his energies and efforts to achieve happiness.

B. Compensation

Compensation is all benefits that are earned by workers/employees which correspond to services they provide to a company. Compensation may cover a greater purpose than reward or income. While rewards or income primarily refers to the financial benefit, compensation may cover both financial or non-financial aspects.

C. Job satisfaction

According to Pramudena (2019), job satisfaction can also instill a strong commitment to employees. On the other hand, if an employee is not satisfied, it will result in insufficient commitment. Job satisfaction is an emotional response to a profession that includes cognitive, affective, and social life responses or actions.

D. Work performance

The ability is indicated with job performance or actual performance (an actual result of an activity personally achieved). Ability is the result of activities based on quality parameter as well as an employee's achievement in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities an organization has assigned (Mangkunegara, 2017:67).

E. Theoretical framework

Figure 1: The theoretical framework of the research

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research category

This research was conducted using a quantitative method. According to Sugiyono (2015), the quantitative procedure is also known as the conventional method because it has been used for quite a long time as a research method. This procedure is regarded as the objective method (scientific) because it has fulfilled the objective requirements, such as concrete or empirical, objective, measurable, logical, and analytical method. As a result, it can be achieved through the latest knowledge, insights, and technology. It is called quantitative method because the information resulting in a study is in the form of numbers as well as statistical analysis. Meanwhile, an analysis in this study was conducted using a survey method by random sampling to the employees from all divisions of the BPN, the Regency of Bekasi.

B. Population and sample

The population is a complete sub-group, generally comprising people, objects, or events of interest in studying or becoming research objects. The population in this research is the employees of BPN of the Regency of Bekasi, accounting for 140 employees. Meanwhile, the illustration is a part or division of the population that is observed.

C. Method of data analysis

The procedure of data processing used in this research is performed using the software of SPSS version 24. There are several stages of data processing in this research consisting of research validity test, reliability test, classical assumptions test (i.e., normality, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity), path analysis, coefficient of confidence, and the assumption test using the simultaneous F test as well as the partial t test.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Validity and reliability

1. Validity test

Validity test is performed to measure whether a questionnaire is valid/reliable. The questionnaire is said to be reliable provided that it is able to deliver something that will be measured. Furthermore, according to Kasmadi and Sunariah (2014:79), in the Product Moment Relationship method, an indicator to measure validity is that the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, provided that:

$N = 103$ or $df = 103 - 2 = 101$, the r_{table} value obtained = 0.193. Furthermore, the values are compared between that of r_{count} and r_{table} .

$R_{count} > (0.193) = \text{valid}$

$R_{count} < (0.193) = \text{invalid}$

2. Reliability test

In the reliability test, the data were processed using the software of SPSS version 24. If the value of Cronbach's alpha accounts for 0.6, it is regarded to be reliable. The reliability test results of all items are regarded to be reliable. Therefore, the next step is to measure the information reliability. In carrying out the reliability test, the population accounts for 103 respondents. The basis of decision making is:

- a. If r_{alpha} (Cronbach's alpha) is positive, and $r_{alpha} > 0.6$, the item is considered to be reliable.
- b. If r_{alpha} (Cronbach's alpha) is negative and $r_{alpha} < 0.6$, the item is regarded to be unreliable.

Table 5: Reliability test results

No.	Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Minimum Cronbach's alpha	Note
1.	Work motivation	0.691	0.6	Reliable
2.	Compensation	0.692	0.6	Reliable
3.	Job satisfaction	0.670	0.6	Reliable
4.	Performance	0.668	0.6	Reliable

Source: research data processed, 2020

B. Classical Assumption test

1. Normality test

The Kolmogorov – Smirnov test shows that the significance level of the unstandardized residual is 0.200, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the data are normally distributed. Thus, the variable estimator obtained in this study is considered unbiased or nearly approaches the number of actual population and the data are normally distributed.

2. Heteroscedasticity test

The determination of whether there is heteroscedasticity is by observing the dots pattern in the regression scatterplots obtained from SPSS. If there is a unique pattern, the regression has indicated heteroscedasticity. On the other hand, if there is no real pattern and the points are scattered above and below the zero value and on the Y-axis, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity.

Figure 2: Heteroscedasticity test result

Source: Research data processed, 2020

The results of the heteroscedasticity test indicate that scattering dots are showing an unreal pattern above and below the value of 0 on the Y axis. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity issue in the regression form.

3. Multicollinearity test

According to Priyatno (2016: 130), the multicollinearity test is a condition where between two or more free elasticity, there is a perfect or nearly perfect linear relationship is formed in the regression. A good regression form is indicated with the absence of a multicollinearity issue. The determination of whether there is multicollinearity is usually performed by observing the tolerance and VIF value in the linear regression results. If the value of tolerance is more than 0.1 and VIF is less than 10, there is no multicollinearity.

Table 6: Multicollinearity test result

Coefficients^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Work motivation	.655	1.527
	Compensation	.607	1.646
	Job satisfaction	.460	2.174

a. Dependent variable: work performance

Source: Research data processed, 2020

By observing Table 6, it can be seen that the tolerance value of the two independent variables and the intervening variable is more than 0.1. Furthermore, the value of VIF is less than 10, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity problem in the regression model.

C. Path analysis

Analysis of the causal relationship between the variables of work motivation and compensation on job satisfaction and performance is performed through a method called path analysis. Based on the analysis results of data from questionnaires processed with the software SPSS, the study obtained as follows:

Table 7: Determination coefficient of substructure 1

Model summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error of the estimate
1	.735 ^a	.540	.531	3.656

a. Predictors: (constant), compensation, work motivation
b. Dependent variable: job satisfaction

Source: research data processed, 2020

Based on Table 7, it can be observed that there is a simultaneous effect of motivation and compensation on job satisfaction with a level of confidence of 0.540 and the residual coefficient of $1 - R^2 = 0.460$. The elasticity of work motivation and compensation accounts for 54% to the job satisfaction. On the other hand, the other effect of 46% is influenced by other factors not determined in this study.

Table 8: Determination coefficient of substructure 2

Model summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.557 ^a	.310	.297	4.760

a. Predictors: (constant), compensation, work motivation
b. Dependent variable: performance

Source: research data processed, 2020

Based on Table 8, it can be observed that the variables of work motivation and compensation have a simultaneous effect on ability at the level of confidence of 0.310, while the magnitude of the residual coefficient is $1 - R^2 = 0.690$. Work motivation and compensation share a 31% effect on the employees' competence. Meanwhile, another 69% factor is influenced by other variables not determined in this study.

D. Hypotheses testing

1. Partial t-test

Table 9: The t partial test results of the variable of work motivation on work performance

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	Beta			
	Motivasi Kerja	.587	7.293	.000

Source: Research data processed, 2020

The route coefficient as a direct effect of work motivation to job satisfaction is 0.587, proving that employees' increase in work motivation will result in job satisfaction. In addition, it obtained a t-count of 7.293 at the level of significance of 5% and the value of the t-table of 1.983. Consequently, given t-count = 7.293, which is greater than 1.983, therefore, H₀ is rejected, which proves that the hypothesis (H₁) stating work motivation has a significant effect on the job satisfaction for the BPN employees in the Regency of Bekasi.

Table 10: Partial t-test result of the variable of compensation on job satisfaction

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Standardized coefficients		t	Sig.
	Beta			
	Compensation	.626	8.078	.000

Source: Research data processed, 2020

The route coefficient as a direct effect of compensation on job satisfaction accounts for 0.626. It proves that a continuous increase in compensation given to the employees will result in an increase in job satisfaction with a continuous increase in a p-value of 0.000. The t-count is 8.078 at a significance level of 5%, and the value of the t-table is 1.983. Consequently, since the value of t-count is 8.078 greater than 1.983, H₀ is rejected, indicating that the hypothesis (H₂) stating that compensation has a significant effect on the BPN employees' job satisfaction in the Regency of Bekasi.

Table 11: Partial t-test result of the variable of work motivation on work performance

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Standardized coefficients		t	Sig.
	Beta			
	Work motivation	.482	5.524	.000

Source: Research data processed, 2020

The route coefficient as a direct effect of work motivation on the employees' competence is 0.482, proving that when work motivation continuously increases, the employees' competence will also incline with the p-value of 0.000. In addition, it obtained t-count accounting for 5.524 at the significance level of 5%, the value of t-table of 1.983. Consequently, since the value of t-count = 5.524, greater than 1.983, H₀ is rejected, inferring that the hypothesis (H₃) states that work motivation has a significant effect on the BPN employees' competence in the Regency of Bekasi, is accepted.

Table 12: Partial t-test result of the variable of compensation on the work performance

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Standardized coefficients		t	Sig.
	Beta			
Compensation	.437		4.885	.000

Source: Research data processed, 2020

The route coefficient as a direct effect of compensation on the employees' competence is 0.437, which indicates that if the compensation given to the employees continuously increases, there will be a continuous increase in their competence with a p-value of 0.000, t-count of 4.885 at the significance level of 5% and the value of t-table of 1.983. Consequently, since t-count = 4.885 is greater than 1.983, H₀ is rejected which proves that the hypothesis (H₄) is accepted that the compensation shares an important implication for the BPN employees' competence in the Regency of Bekasi.

Satisfaction on the employees' competence is 0.554. It indicates that an increase in the job satisfaction continuously will improve the employees' competence. In addition, it obtained t-count of 6.682 at a significance level of 5%, the value of the t-table is 1.983. Consequently, since the value of t-count = 6.682 is greater than 1.983, H₀ is rejected, proving that the hypothesis (H₅) is accepted stating that job satisfaction shares important implications for the BPN employees' competence in the Regency of Bekasi.

2. Simultaneous partial F-test

Table 14: Simultaneous partial F-test result of Sub 1

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1568.835	2	784.417	58.698	.000 ^b
	Residual	1336.369	100	13.364		
	Total	2905.204	102			
a. Dependent variable: job satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (constant), compensation, work motivation						

Source: Research data processed, 2020

Based on the table above, it is obtained that the F-count value is 58.69, a p-value of 0.000 with alpha = 0.05, and the degrees of freedom $\nu_1 = 2$ and $\nu_2 = 100$, the F-table of 3.09. Because the value of F-count is greater than F-table, i.e., $58.69 > 3.09$, H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. Thus, there is a simultaneously significant influence of work motivation and compensation on the BPN employees' job satisfaction, the Regency of Bekasi.

Table 15: Simultaneous partial F-test result of Sub 2

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1019.274	2	509.637	22.495	.000 ^b
	Residual	2265.541	100	22.655		
	Total	3284.816	102			
a. Dependent variable: work performance						
b. Predictors: (constant), compensation, work motivation						

Source: Research data processed, 2020

Based on the results in the table above, it is obtained that the F-count value is 22.49, a p-value of 0.000 with $\alpha = 0.05$ and the degrees of freedom $\nu_1 = 2$ and $\nu_2 = 100$. Meanwhile, the F-table is 3.09. Because the value of F-count is greater than that of F-table, i.e., $24.49 > 3.09$, H_0 is rejected while H_1 is accepted. Thus, there is a simultaneously significant influence of work motivation and compensation on the BPN employees' work performance in the Regency of Bekasi.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results, considering theoretical elaboration to data collection, data presentation as well as analysis and discussion, we can conclude several points as follows:

1. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the BPN employees' job satisfaction in the Regency of Bekasi.
2. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on the BPN employees' job satisfaction in the Regency of Bekasi.
3. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the BPN employees' work performance in the Regency of Bekasi.
4. Compensation has a positive and significant effect on the BPN employees' work performance in the Regency of Bekasi.
5. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the BPN employees' work performance in the Regency of Bekasi.
6. Work motivation and compensation simultaneously have a significant effect on the BPN employees' job satisfaction in the Regency of Bekasi.
7. Work motivation and compensation simultaneously have a significant effect on the BPN employees' work performance in the Regency of Bekasi.

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